

Impact of Media Coverage of Covid-19 Pandemic on its Risk Perception in Mumbai city

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Abstract: People in India have always relied on the news media to learn more about the lethality and trajectory of the evolution of Covid-19 virus. Post-pandemic, viewers and readers, especially young adults, spend significantly higher number of hours in front of the television and newspapers(online) than they did before. Hence, people could be more vulnerable to the information provided by the news media related to the transmissibility, fatality and evolution of the virus. This study invokes the 'cultivation theory' as its theoretical foundation, which postulates that the heavy consumers of media cultivate their sense of reality based on what the media portrays. The study aimed to understand if the impact of headlines and news stories in print and electronic media on Covid-19 among other sources of influence have specially impacted the level of anxiety and fear over the spread of the virus amongst the consumers of such media in Mumbai. A quantitative methodology was adopted that provided with an objective and numerical picture of the threat perception of Covid-19, what they believe/fear the disease can do to them and the extent to which they attribute it to the information received through various sources. The data was collected from 250 respondents using a questionnaire prepared taking reference from the "Standard questionnaire on risk perception of an infectious disease outbreak". The second part of the questionnaire had follow-up questions to the risk perception measurement scale that attempted to find its co-relations with various source influences. The findings suggested that print and electronic media were not a significantly different source of influence on the risk perception of Mumbaikars. Furthermore, there is a multiplicity of the sources of influence that has significantly diluted the impact of any one particular source of influence on the threat perception of people.

Keywords: Media Coverage of Epidemics, Corona Media Coverage, Sources of Influence, Risk perception of epidemics and role of media

Introduction

We have witnessed an unprecedented disruption caused by a pandemic of incredible magnitude and this continues to have a serious impact on the socio-political and economic standing of our nation. It won't be an overstatement to say that the Covid-19 pandemic may even lead to significant psychological effects on certain sections of the society, especially the ones belonging to the worst-affected cities. And media remains at the forefront of such a phenomenon, being the primary influencer of people's perception of this virus and its effects on them.

Mumbai has always been one of the hardest hit cities when it comes to Covid-19 virus and its variants, with the city often having recorded the highest number of cases and casualties

in the entire country. This had repeatedly brought about the city to a literal standstill unlike any other city with a history of the maximum number of containment zones once again in the country. The work-from-home phenomenon, a natural consequence of the pandemic, has driven people in the city to spend higher number of hours in front of the television and seek out online version of the newspapers, as well as receive information from social media and news applications. It is important to understand that the newspapers and news channels have unfailingly reported the emergence of new variants virus (such as variants of interest and variants of concern), count of active cases, as well as the covid-induced deaths as one of its lead stories.

Whenever an epidemic hit a nation or a city, the risk perception held by the citizens play a crucial role in the way they make decisions. The risk perception therefore becomes an important measure of understanding the psychological state of the people affected by such a pandemic. The degree to which an individual feels that he is vulnerable to the virus, the extent to which he feels the virus is fatal can affect the actions that he takes during such a period. This in turn could impact the governmental policies. Studies have told us that among the various influences, media continues to be one of the important shapers of the opinion that an individual holds in regard to the epidemic. There are several influences that affect people during an epidemic, but news medium assumes itself to be the primary deliverer of information and, in it, may be present a sensationalistic angle or frame that could have a considerable impact on the threat perceived by the individual of the disease. This study therefore aims to understand if the impact of such headlines and news stories related to Covid-19 among other sources of influence have specially impacted the level of anxiety and fear over the spread of the virus amongst the consumers of such media in Mumbai

Literature Review

Key words: Media Coverage of Epidemics, Corona Media Coverage, Sources of Influence, Risk perception of epidemics and role of media

Media Coverage of Epidemics

Earlier research suggests that the coverage of epidemics by the media, especially newspapers, have been found to be in a mixed, neutral light.

Garett in her article titled “Understanding Media’s Response to Epidemics” published in the year 2001, asserts media to be a softener of the panic than a causer of it during an epidemic. The article tries to address the popular perception of the media in the eyes of the state and its citizens, which is as a trouble maker. The author claims that the idea or concept of ‘quarantine’ itself elicits negative reactions and a sense of panic among people. Media doesn’t require to play a significant role to amplify this sentiment. Especially, when

it comes in relation to Americans, the idea of confiscation of civil liberties or any kind of sequestration is associated majorly with criminal behavior and therefore they are always having a negative perception to the concept of quarantine regardless of the way it is covered by the media. Another reference is made by the author to a mystery virus that floated in Surat, India, in 1994, which when was broadcasted through BBC had created a mass panic. The author also stresses on the relationship between a large release and panic when it comes to an epidemic with media having no role in contributing to it. The length of the pandemic is also looked upon as a factor that affect the patience levels of the media and its readers. The author considers media to be playing the role of a “bridge of trust” between the government and its citizens. (Garrett, 2001)

Yotam Ophir in his (2018) study on the effect of American news coverage of epidemics had analyzed the content of 5006 articles of leading American publication that had covered three major pandemics that rocked the world before Corona, which were H1N1, Ebola, and Zika. The study found that the articles lacked a comprehensive angle to their stories and had restricted lens through which it analyzed stories. For instance, articles that primarily were on social and economic disruptions failed to discuss its health implications. One of the important findings were that very few articles talked about how could an individual reduce the risk of contracting the virus, which created a sense of helplessness amongst its readers, and could contribute to the risk perception and anxiety levels of the readers. (Ophir, 2018)

A 2008 study by Tsung-jen, Rosalyna and Dominique on the media coverage of public health epidemics majorly focused on “framing” and “issue-attention cycle” as the key theoretical framework w.r.t to coverage of three major epidemics: The mad cow disease, Avian flu and West Nile virus. It tried to examine the frames used by journalist and newspapers to cover epidemics. The study classified the frames used by the newspapers in to six categories: “Consequence”, “Uncertainty”, “Action”, “Reassurance”, “Conflict” and “New Evidence”. The study did a content analysis of 688 new stories that appeared in “The New York Times” from 1996-2005. The study concluded that “Consequence” and “Action” were the major frames used consistently by the newspapers in covering the three epidemics. Which meant that stories dominantly had a focus on socio-political and economic impact of the epidemic as well as the action taken against the diseases. Rise in the number of cases, policy announcements by the government and discovery of scientific evidences dominated the news coverage. (Shih, Wijaya, & Brossard, 2008)

A paper on “the social impact of disease on Newspaper Coverage” (2000) by Adelman and Verbrugge looked at social history of prominent diseases, epidemiological rates and newspaper coverage, and tried to produce an integrated analysis. The study found out that diseases with high mortality rate generated maximum coverage. It tended to have death

content in the news stories. The study established a close relationship between news coverage and epidemiology. (Adelman & Verbrugge, Sep., 2000)

Media Coverage of Covid-19 Pandemic

The literature on the media coverage of the pandemic is not quite vast. As a result, a definitive conclusion cannot be made on the nature of media's coverage of this particular epidemic.

A particularly relevant research was a 2019 case study of media coverage of Covid-19 outbreak in China. The study was interested in finding out the impact of western media coverage of corona pandemic on the Chinese community. The study deemed the western media coverage to be misleading and racially discriminatory. It claimed that such kind of misleading coverage by the western media impacted Chinese people living abroad, it led to "inequitable" treatments of focal communities and also suggested a possible impact on the mental health of Chinese population living abroad as well the ones returning to the country. (Wen, Aston, Liu, & Tianyu, 2020)

Time Magazine did a comparative analysis of the media coverage of Covid-19 with Ebola (2018), it found that the coverage of Covid-19 was extremely different than that of the Ebola outbreak in 2018. The news articles in English language were 23 times higher than that of Ebola in the first month of its outbreak. This suggest that Corona's impact has been far more wide-spread than Ebola. The article based on this study also stated that Corona outbreak coverage has been more sensationalistic than that of Ebola. (Ducharme, 2020)

A state level content analysis done on the coverage of Covid-19 in the leading Malayalam dailies in Kerala found that news articles were reliant greatly on views of the health experts. However, the study also pointed towards agenda being set when it came to reporting news events related to Covid-19. (Kb & Rajkamal, 2020)

Sources of Influence for People During Epidemics

Studies have suggested that the information needs of people, especially of vulnerable populations, rise during the time of a pandemic. All the recent studies available conducted were during the period of Swine Flu (H1N1) pandemic, which have definitively stated that Television and Newspaper followed by the Internet have been the major sources of information and influence for the public w.r.t to the outbreak.

A study by Li Ping Wong and I-Ching Sam on the Public Sources of Information during the H1N1 influenza investigated upon the "sources of information and the information needs" during H1N1 influenza. They did a cross sectional interview of 1050 respondents residing in Malaysia. Television and Newspaper were found to be as the major sources through which the people received information during the outbreak. Low-education group

was found to be relying on television medium for obtaining more information than the high-education group. Family played a significant role in enhancing knowledge related to the epidemic and taking preventive action towards it. The study also found that there was a dearth for information emerging from healthcare providers which was sought after by the people. The study established a correlation between increasing level of information received and increased level of fearfulness. This particular finding has particular significance for the assumptions made by the present study. (Wong LP, 2010)

A study done on the identification of the chief sources of information resorted to by susceptible population during the H1N1 pandemic using the face-to-face interviews of 216 respondents from the counties of Mississippi concluded that television was the dominant medium followed by newspaper and the internet. (Freiman AJ, 2011)

The online medium of Youtube was studied as source of information during the first phase of H1N1 pandemic. The efficaciousness of Youtube as a source of information about the pandemic was being looked at in this research. It was found that 61 percentage of videos on Youtube had information that was considered useful whereas the rest was found to be misleading. (Pandey, Patni, Singh, Sood, & Singh, 2010)

Risk Perception of Epidemics and The Role of Media

The definitions of risk perceptions in the majority of literature surveyed have centered around the perceptions of vulnerability and susceptibility. When it comes to literature specifically in the field of ‘health psychology’, risk perception is often defined as “as estimates of likelihood / chances, or beliefs about vulnerability / susceptibility”. (Shiloh, 2013) (Kwak MS, 2009) (Hay J, 2006). The study titled “Risk perception and disease spread on social networks” by Kitchovitcha and Lio, define ‘risk perception’ as “information concerning the disease which drives an individual to take measures in order to reduce his susceptibility to infection”. The investigation tried to focus on the risk perception model on a social network and its relation to spread of diseases. The study established that level of alertness of an individual had an effect on the spread of the disease. (Kitchovitch & Lio, 2010) .

A major study in 2009 on risk perception related to SARS and infectious Diseases conducted an international survey of 3,346 respondents to measure five components of risk and threat perception of major infectious diseases in. The five components measured in the study were: “perceived threat”, “vulnerability”, “severity”, “response efficacy”, and “self-efficacy”. The study had concluded that there was significantly high level of risk perceived for SARS epidemic. It was also found that the threat perceived varied between European countries and Asian countries. (de Zwart, 2009)

The role of media and social media in particular have been found to be particularly crucial

source of influence during any kind of epidemic. A survey of research on the effect of media on risk perception in 2011 found media to be one amongst the various important influencers of people's risk perception. The content of media was found to be inobjective when it came to presentation of risks. The vivid nature of media's description and the frequency played a role in affecting risk perception of its readers. (Wahlberg & Sjoberg, 2011)

Social media's role on influencing risk perception during the MERS outbreak in South Korea was found to be significant, as the popularity of social media had a positive correlation on the risk perception formation. The user's cognitive characteristic was identified in the study as an important factor w.r.t impact of social media on the user's risk perception. (Choi, Yoo, Noh, & Park, 2017) Fear and anger were identified as two important emotions by another study looking at the impact of social media on risk perception, and these two emotions were found to be playing a significant role of mediation between social media consumption and risk perception. (Oh, Lee, & Han, 2020)

The survey of all the studies points in the direction of media playing an important role as one of the chief sources of influence during the prevalence of a highly viral disease. One may infer that media coverage of epidemics does have a psychological impact on the reader, especially on his perceived vulnerability and severity of the disease. The studies also have mentioned the unmistakable presence of higher levels risk perception that people have held during the earlier outbreaks.

Therefore, the following hypothesis is drawn on the basis of the literature review:

Hypothesis

H₀: The news stories and headlines on Covid-19 pandemic in the electronic and print media don't significantly affect the risk perception amongst its audience in Mumbai

H_A: The news stories and headlines on Covid-19 pandemic in the electronic and print media significantly affect the risk perception amongst its audience in Mumbai

Theoretical Framework of the Study

Cultivation theory developed by George Gerbner is the central to the assumptions made by this study. Cultivation theory posits that television heavily influences and even cultivates the sense of social reality of the viewers of this medium. The theory hypothesizes that belief and assumptions developed by viewers of the social reality is heavily influenced by the most repeated values and messages broadcasted by television. The theory also asserts that the media creates and displays the image of the world which is not completely reflective of reality. (Gerbner, Gross, & Morgan, 1986)

People in general have gathered information about Covid-19 primarily based on the coverage of it by the news media. Cultivation theory especially gains importance with higher time spent at residences post the pandemic, especially due to the work from home phenomenon. Viewers and readers invariably end up spending significantly higher number of hours in front of the television and newspapers(online). As a result, people may be more vulnerable to the information provided by the news media, which according to the cultivation theory, could have them heavily influenced by the image of Covid-19 and the lethality associated with it presented by the news media.

Operational Definitions

For the purposes of this study, *risk perception* was broken down into six quantifiable sub-variables. They are as follows: “*Perceived severity*”, “*Perceived vulnerability*”, “*Perception of vulnerability for parents*”, “*Comparative vulnerability*”, “*Perceived Susceptibility*” and “*Fear of Immediate recurrence*”. The other sub-variables which were closely associated to threat perception were “Response efficacy” and “Self- efficacy”. The sub-variables were borrowed from the “Standard questionnaire on risk perception of an infectious disease outbreak” and from a study titled “Perceived Threat, Risk Perception, and Efficacy Beliefs Related to SARS and Other Infectious Diseases: Results of an International Survey”. The components were adapted in relation to the current context and state of pandemic in the city of Mumbai. (ECOM- Effective Communication in Outbreak Management for Europe- TOOL-QUESTIONNAIRE, 2015) (de Zwart, 2009)

The sub- variables are defined as follows:

1. **Perceived Severity:** It is defined as “the physical seriousness of the disease, its medical and clinical consequences”. (ECOM- Effective Communication in Outbreak Management for Europe- TOOL-QUESTIONNAIRE, 2015) (de Zwart, 2009)
2. **Perceived susceptibility:** It is defined as “an individual’s chances (that are related to physical predisposition) of contracting the disease during a certain period in the near future”. (ECOM- Effective Communication in Outbreak Management for Europe- TOOL-QUESTIONNAIRE, 2015)
3. **Perception of susceptibility for parents:** It is defined as “an individual parent’s chances (that are related to physical predisposition) of contracting the disease during a certain period in the near future”. (ECOM- Effective Communication in Outbreak Management for Europe- TOOL-QUESTIONNAIRE, 2015)
4. **Perceived vulnerability:** It is defined as “an individual’s chances (that are related to external factors) of contracting the disease during a certain period in the near future”.

(ECOM- Effective Communication in Outbreak Management for Europe- TOOL-QUESTIONNAIRE, 2015)

5. **Perceived Comparative Vulnerability:** It is defined as “an individual’s chances (that are related to external factors) of contracting the disease compared to people of his age during a certain period in the near future”. (de Zwart, 2009)
6. **Perceived Response efficacy:** It is defined as “an estimate of whether the respondent thinks he/she is able to carry out the preventive measure”. (ECOM- Effective Communication in Outbreak Management for Europe- TOOL-QUESTIONNAIRE, 2015)
7. **Perceived Self- efficacy:** It is defined as “an estimate of whether the respondent thinks he/she is able to carry out the preventive measure”. (ECOM- Effective Communication in Outbreak Management for Europe- TOOL-QUESTIONNAIRE, 2015)
8. **Fear of Immediate recurrence:** It is defined as the fear of the virus re-emerging after a short duration

Research Design

Considering the nature of findings that the study seeks, the research design used was a descriptive one as the study intended to understand the impact of news media coverage of Covid-19 pandemic on the way people have perceived the risks and threats associated with the disease.

Research Questions

RQ1: What is the role of media in influencing the perception of self-efficacy and response efficacy w.r.t Covid-19 in Mumbai?

RQ2: What is the dominant source of influence on the risk perception of Mumbaikars when it comes to Covid-19 pandemic?

Methodology

A quantitative methodology was adopted for the study with the objective of collecting numerical data received through the questionnaire to statistically test the hypothesis. The quantitative methodology provided with an objective and numerical picture of the threat perception of Covid-19. A quantitative assessment was conducted of the above-mentioned sub-variables of risk perception: *perceived severity*, *perceived susceptibility*, *perceived susceptibility of parents*, *perceived vulnerability*, *perceived comparative vulnerability*, *perceived response efficacy*, *perceived self-efficacy*, and *fear of immediate recurrence*. The data was collected using a questionnaire prepared taking reference from the “Standard

questionnaire on risk perception of an infectious disease outbreak". (ECOM- Effective Communication in Outbreak Management for Europe- TOOL-QUESTIONNAIRE, 2015) The questionnaire was administered to respondents that measured the above mentioned eight components. Since Likert scale was used as the scaling technique, the type of data received was ordinal. The second part of the survey had follow-up questions to the risk perception- questions that attempted to find its co-relations with sources of influence (sub groups of independent variable) that were: *News headlines and News stories, WHO & ICMR reports and publications, Government announcements and statements, and Family/Friends*, which were the groups of independent variable. The type of data received was nominal for the follow-up question.

Sampling

The universe of the study was all citizens of Mumbai district who consumed electronic and online media(news-websites/e-newspaper) and are between the age group of 18-50. The reason for such a sweeping age bracket was because of how Covid-19 indiscriminately affected the lives of everyone in the world, with age-groups barely becoming a variable. Due to time and cost constraints, as well as the gargantuan size of the population, a non-probability sampling technique was adopted. Convenience sampling was selected as the elements of the population were readily available as well as faster and easier to access. The sample size of the study was 250. It must be noted that 95 percent of the respondents of the study were between the age group of 18-25. One of the limitations of this sampling technique is that of representativeness and unknown degree of sampling error. However, studies also suggest that in instances where the phenomenon studied is quite universal and wide-spread, which in this case is an epidemic, a convenient sampling technique is able to overcome most of its limitations of representativeness.

Measures

Risk Perception

Following questions were presented to the respondents (based on the standard risk perception questionnaire) to measure the risk perception that was subdivided into sub-variables.

Severity: How serious (on a scale from 1 to 10) would it be for you if you contracted Corona in next one month?"

Perceived Susceptibility: How likely do you think (on a scale from 1 to 5; 1 being Highly unlikely and 5 being Highly likely) it is that you could face a fatal risk if you contracted COVID-19 in the next one month?

Perceived Susceptibility for parents: How fatal a risk (on a scale from 1 to 5) do you

think your parent or an elderly relative could face if he/she contracted COVID-19 in the next one month? (on a scale from 1 to 5)

Perceived vulnerability: How likely do you think (on a scale from 1 to 5) it is that you could contract COVID-19 in the next one month?

Perceived Comparative vulnerability: How likely do you think (on a scale from 1 to 5) it is that you will contract COVID-19 in next one month compared to other [women/men] of your age in Mumbai?

Response Efficacy: To what extent do you think (on a scale from 1 to 5; 1 being not at all, 5 being very much) people can take effective actions to prevent the contraction of COVID-19?

Self-efficacy: How confident (on a scale from 1 to 5; 1 being not confident, 5 being very confident) are you that you can prevent contracting the virus in the scenario where the person in your neighborhood is infected with it?

Fear of immediate recurrence: How likely (on a scale from 1 to 5) is it that you would step out for work/socialization the very next day a curfew is lifted? (ECOM- Effective Communication in Outbreak Management for Europe- TOOL-QUESTIONNAIRE, 2015)

Sources of Influence

Following were the follow-up questions presented to the each of the earlier questions to find out the sources of influence: In relation to previous question, which of the options mentioned below do you think played a bigger role in helping you assess the likelihood?

News headlines and News stories, WHO & ICMR reports and publications, Government announcements and statements, Family/Friends, Can't decide and Others

Data & Analysis

For the analysis, SPSS was used to conduct the Kruskal – Wallis test, the non-parametric alternative to the one-way ANOVA. Non-parametric test is used when the data is non-normally distributed. The independent variable – Source of Influence has multiple independent sub groups like Family and Friends, Reports of ICMR and WHO, Statements made by Government Officials about COVID-19, News Headlines and stories related to COVID-19. This variable is nominal in nature.

The dependent variable is measured on ordinal scale. i.e. with the help of ranks. The dependent variable is the level of Risk perception in Mumbai, which is broken down into sub variables: Perceived Severity, Perceived Susceptibility, Perceived Vulnerability,

Perceived susceptibility for parents, Comparative Vulnerability, Fear of immediate recurrence.

To examine the hypothesized relationship, Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted to determine if there are statistically significant differences between the groups of the independent variable on the ordinal dependent sub variables. The test was run on all the dependent sub variables. The test statistic and the asymptotic significance (p value) was computed with significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ for all the 6 dependent sub variables to see if News Headlines and news stories related to COVID-19 pandemic significantly affect the risk perception than the other Sources of Influence in Mumbai. The same was also analyzed using box plot diagram.

Results

Dependent sub- variable 1: Perceived Severity

It was tested if Headlines and the stories on the rise of COVID-19 infections and deaths in newspapers and news channels had a significantly different distribution across categories of sources of influence. The results showed that Perceived severity was the same across all categories/groups of Sources of influence. The test statistic was lower than critical chi-square value. Hence, null hypothesis was retained. $\chi^2 (3) = 6.160$, p value= 0.104 is higher than significance level $\alpha = 0.05$ which calls for the same decision rule.

Dependent sub-variable 2: Perceived Susceptibility

The results showed that the distribution of Perceived susceptibility was the same across all categories of Sources of Influence. Hence, null hypothesis is accepted. Perceived susceptibility was not significantly different for News headlines and stories on the rise of COVID-19 infections and deaths in news media; $\chi^2 (3) = 2.4733$, p value= 0.480, $\alpha = 0.05$

Dependent sub-variable 3: Perceived Vulnerability

The results showed that the distribution of Perceived vulnerability was the same across all categories of sources of influence. Hence, null hypothesis is accepted. Perceived vulnerability was not significantly different for Headlines and news stories on coronavirus count and containment zones. $\chi^2 (3) = 2.3359$, p value= 0.670, $\alpha = 0.05$

Dependent sub-variable 4: Perceived Susceptibility for Parents

The results showed that the distribution of Perceived Susceptibility of Parents was not the same across all categories of Source of influence. Hence, null hypothesis was rejected. $\chi^2 (3) = 16.157$, p value= 0.003, $\alpha = 0.05$

To measure the level of difference between different groups, a post hoc analysis was

conducted in which pairwise comparisons were made to examine the differences between independent groups of Sources of Influence. The significance values have been adjusted by the Bonferroni correction for multiple tests. It can be examined from the pairwise comparisons that the Source of Influence-Family and Friends is significantly different from Can't decide; Adjusted p value= 0.007. Another Source of influence- Statements made by Government health officials on the high risk faced by senior citizens is significantly different from Family and Friends; Adjusted p value= 0.004. The Figure 1 also shows the sample average ranks for the Sources of Influence. The highest average mean rank is for Family and Friends; 170.59. The second highest average mean rank is of News Stories on high mortality rate and high percentage of deaths of senior citizens; 135.55. News Stories and News headlines in this case does have a higher risk perception in Mumbai but the dominant Source of influence is Family and Friends.

Figure 1

Dependent sub-variable 5: Perception of Comparative Vulnerability

The results showed that the distribution of Perception of comparative vulnerability was the same across all categories of sources of influence. Hence, null hypothesis is accepted. Perceived comparative vulnerability was not significantly different for News stories on the age group analysis of COVID-19 infected patients in newspapers; $\chi^2(3) = 1.839$, p value= 0.606, $\alpha = 0.05$

Dependent sub-variable 6: Fear of immediate recurrence

The results showed that the distribution of Fear of immediate recurrence was the same across all categories of source of influence. Hence, null hypothesis is accepted. Fear of immediate recurrence was not significantly different for the source of influence – News stories on the countries where Lockdown was lifted and the current state; $\chi^2 (2) = 3.802$, p value= 0.149, $\alpha= 0.05$

The Box plot diagrams (next page) for these 6 dependent sub-variables also depict that there are no significant differences across distributions of the sources of influence. The median value is also equal across different sources of influence in different dependent sub-variables. Figure 2 indicates that all the sources of influence are negatively skewed. In figure 3, all sources of influence are positively skewed.

Figure 4, all sources of influence are positively skewed. In figure 5, all sources of influence are negatively skewed. Figure 6 and 7, the distribution is approximately symmetric.

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Conclusion

Analyzing data collected for Mumbai during the Covid-19 pandemic, this study attempted to find the impact of News headlines and News stories on risk perception in Mumbai. The findings indicated that news headlines and news stories related to COVID-19 pandemic were not significantly affecting the risk perception with respect to 5 dependent sub-variables- Perceived severity, perceived vulnerability, perceived susceptibility, comparative vulnerability and fear of immediate recurrence. Therefore, the hypothesis that News headlines and News stories in the times of global pandemic would significantly affect the risk perception amongst its consumers stood rejected.

It was also found that there is no single dominant source of influence for all the sub-variables of risk perception. The results state that there is a multiplicity of the sources of influence, which have significantly diluted the impact of one particular source of influence. Hence, it could be concluded that news media headlines and stories don't appear to be a dominant source of influence on the risk perception in the study. It doesn't play a unique role in comparison to other sources while affecting the level of anxiety and vulnerability perceived by people in Mumbai w.r.t Covid-19 pandemic.

The 6th dependent sub-variable- Perceived Susceptibility for Parents showed differences in the distribution of the different sources of influence. The dominant source of influence for this sub-variable was Family and friends and the second dominant source was News Stories on high mortality rate and high percentage of deaths of senior citizens.

The box plots reveal that for all the dependent sub-variables of risk perception the median is equal across different sources of influence except Perceived susceptibility of parents.

The role of media in influencing the perception of self-efficacy and response efficacy was not found to be significantly different from other sources of influence. Media didn't play any unique role in people's perception of the likelihood of taking preventive measures against the pandemic. The median for response efficacy was 4, which meant that people affected by all the sources of influence majorly think that people are in good position to take effective actions to prevent the contraction of COVID-19. However, the median for Self Efficacy is 3, which means that people affected by different groups of source of influence are neutral when it comes to preventing the contraction of virus in case a person in neighborhood is infected with it. This means the perception of self-efficacy is higher than response efficacy in Mumbai.

Limitations and Future scope

One of the shortcomings of the study is that respondents may not be always be able to make an accurate estimation on pinning down the most dominant source of influence when it comes to the level of risk they perceive w.r.t Covid-19, there are several factors at play and they may not be able to always distinguish each of them amongst the blend of influences that affect them. With an epidemic as dynamic as covid-19, the status of its impact on the responses fluctuate with every passing day, therefore the results of the study can't be generalized after particular period of time, Social media was not looked separately as a factor that could be a popular factor affecting the risk perception of the dominant number of respondents who have filled the survey questions, therefore that is another limitation of the study, which can also present itself as a future scope for further investigation. The risk perception of Covid-19 for people above 50 may also be significantly different since it impacts them more severely, this study has not looked at this age-group in particular, and could also be considered as future area for this particular study.

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Foot Notes

Critical chi-square value= 7.815; df=3, $\alpha= 0.05$

Critical chi-square value= 5.991; df=2, $\alpha= 0.05$